

Enhanced Robustness in Model Predictive Control of Water Quality Using Adaptive Estimation Methods

Demetrios G. Eliades, Evripides C. Kyriakides & Marios M. Polycarpou
Electrical and Computer Engineering Dept., University of Cyprus, Cyprus

ABSTRACT: In this paper the issue of designing algorithms for controlling the spatial-temporal distribution of chlorine residual in drinking water distribution networks is examined. The network dynamics are influenced by unknown time-varying water demands. A solution methodology is presented using model predictive control principles combined with on-line adaptive forecasting of the system hydraulics as they are driven by consumer demands. The periodic nature of water demands allows the use of Fourier series and Radial Basis Functions with adaptive coefficients for forecasting future demand patterns in the distribution network. The feedback control objective is to maintain chlorine residuals, which acts as a disinfectant for enhanced water quality, within certain lower and upper bounds. Simulation results on a real distribution network are used to illustrate the performance of the proposed feedback control algorithm under unknown water demands and the trade-offs involved in the robust model predictive control methodology.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper demonstrates a control methodology for regulating chlorine concentration in Drinking Water Distribution Networks (DWDN), when influenced by time-varying hydraulic dynamics. Because water can be a carrier of pathogens or other substances that can harm human and animal health, it is important to take necessary actions in order to deliver clean and safe water to the consumers. This is achieved by treating water with a disinfectant substance, such as chlorine, in order to neutralize the micro-organisms and other chemical agents so that they are well below the safety concentrations, as specified by the European Commission (EC, 1998) and the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, 1998).

Typically, when water is taken from reservoirs or rivers, it is disinfected in treatment plants. Disinfectants such as chlorine decay by reacting with other substances, therefore its concentration is reduced. Hence, extra disinfectant injections are needed in tanks or at certain junctions in the DWDN. Unfortunately, chlorine produces by-products such as trihalomethanes when reacting with organic substances. Research has shown that there is a positive association of chlorine by-products with bladder and rectal cancer in humans (Morris et al., 1992). It is therefore crucial to maintain chlorine concentrations within certain bounds so that the water is clean while by-products

concentration is minimized.

Maintaining a chlorine residual throughout the DWDN is a control problem of regulating the spatial-temporal distribution of disinfectant across the DWDN at a certain concentration and within bounds. This is achieved by computing the quantity of chlorine injected by the booster stations at each time step into the network. Due to the fact that large transport time-delays and storage tanks exist in the network and because the hydraulics are time-varying, influenced by unknown demands, the controller needs to be robust to changes so that the constraints set by the directives are not violated.

Controlling chlorine residuals has gained increasing attention in recent years. A number of studies examined the problem in an off-line framework in order to find a chlorine input scheduling algorithm, using optimization techniques such as linear programming (Boccelli et al., 1998, Constans et al., 2003), least squares (Propato & Uber, 2004), genetic algorithms (Dandy & Hewitson, 2000, Munavalli & Kumar, 2003, Prasad et al., 2004) and goal programming (Agha, 2006, Cozzolino et al., 2005). Optimization of water pumps operation has also been considered for regulating chlorine using nonlinear optimization and genetic algorithms (Ostfeld & Salomons, 2006, Sakarya & Mays, 2000).

Regulating chlorine in a DWDN is the problem of

controlling a system at every time-step, responding accordingly to changes in the system. Some online methodologies such as adaptive and model predictive control have been examined in this context. The adaptive controller presented by Wang et al. (2001) represents periodic uncertainty using Fourier series. The system is identified as an auto-regressive moving average model in a linear framework, for which the unknown coefficients are computed online using parameter estimation techniques. Based on this identification model, an indirect adaptive control law is derived and applied to the system. An extension to the decentralized case is presented by Wang et al. (2006).

A Model Predictive Control (MPC) methodology of this problem was introduced by Brdys et al. (2000, 2001). In their work, uncertainties in time-varying parameters, errors in model structure, actuator and measurements errors have been modelled in a set-bounded approach. Safety zones that narrow the constraints are used in order to deal with the uncertainties, and a mixed integer program is used to solve the optimization problem. A decentralized MPC scheme is also demonstrated (Chang et al., 2003).

This work formulates the online water quality control problem, in a robust MPC framework by using adaptive approximation of Fourier series and radial basis functions for estimating future hydraulic dynamics and demands. Specifically, a realistic DWDN is used, with partially-known internal parameters that are influenced by unknown demands. Furthermore quality and hydraulic sensors as well as chlorine boosting stations are assumed to be installed in certain nodes. The structure of the network is known and is used to describe the system in the MPC. The optimal input of chlorine is computed under the specified upper and lower bounds and applied to the systems, at each time step.

This paper is organized as follows: the controller is outlined in Section 2 and hydraulic dynamics estimation is presented in Section 3. The adaptive forecast of periodic hydraulic dynamics is presented in Section 4. The robust MPC formulation is designed in Section 5. Simulation results are presented in Section 6 and finally, concluding remarks are discussed in Section 7.

2 CONTROLLER DESCRIPTION

A schematic description of the system and the controller is presented in Fig. 1. Quantities of chlorine injected into the DWDN are considered to be the input of the system, $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^M$. For M chlorine injection stations in the network, at each time step the input vector is considered as $u(k) = [u_1(k), u_2(k), \dots, u_M(k)]^T$. This in reality corresponds to the mass of chlorine inserted into the system, or to the increase of the concentration at the point of injection,

depending on the type of actuator used.

Let N_F be the total number of nodes in the network. Junctions, reservoirs and tanks are considered as nodes in this research. The DWDN is influenced by disturbances $d(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_F}$ which represent the unknown water demands at each node. Two kinds of outputs are measured; the hydraulic dynamics $\chi(k)$ and the quality dynamics $y(k)$. For N_H the number of hydraulic sensors installed in nodes or pipes, $\chi(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_H}$ corresponds to the flow and/or pressure measurements. For N_Q the number of nodes with quality sensors installed, $y(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Q}$ corresponds to the chlorine concentrations at those nodes. The adaptive forecasting takes a hydraulic measurement $\chi_i(k)$, for $i = 1, \dots, N_H$ and learns an approximation structure (e.g. a Fourier series) that approximates the original signal. The adaptively computed weights $\hat{\theta}_i(k)$ are used to forecast future hydraulic dynamics for the prediction horizon ρ , such that $\hat{\chi}_i(k+T)$, for $T = 1, \dots, \rho$. The Water Demand Estimation module takes as input the forecasts of $\hat{\chi}(k+T)$ as well as the previous and current measurements of $\chi(k)$, to compute the demand patterns $p_i(k+T)$, for $i = 1, \dots, N_F$. The MPC uses these demand estimations to build a model of the DWDN for the future time steps. A hydraulic and quality simulation tool such as EPANET loaded with the distribution network structure can be used for this purpose. A reference signal w and a set of operational constraints are given to the controller. The prediction error $\hat{n}(k)$, given by the difference of the quality output $y(k)$ with the controller's predicted quality output $\hat{y}(k)$, is also provided to the controller. An optimization algorithm computes the output signal such that the predicted future DWDN quality output $\hat{y}(k)$ is within the pre-specified constraints, following the reference signal $w(k)$.

3 ESTIMATING HYDRAULIC DYNAMICS

According to Walski et al. (2001), the driving force behind the hydraulic dynamics is water consumption or water usage, specifically customer and fire flow demands as well as leakages or unaccounted-for water. Furthermore, parameters such as day of the week, season of the year, temperature, rainfall and others affect requests of water. Since there is not a way to directly measure the quantity of water that exits the DWDN in real time at each location in the network, this must be estimated implicitly.

This estimation can be based on information already accessible; for example, flows and pressures are hydraulic dynamics that are commonly measured in these systems through the use of SCADA systems. Furthermore, the average water demand for a specific node can be acquired by statistical analysis of historical utility billing records. Another piece of information is that water demand varies continuously

Figure 1: Model predictive controller using adaptive forecasting of unknown hydraulic dynamics

throughout the day, and roughly follows a diurnal pattern that is repeated every 24 hours (Walski et al., 2001). There is not a common demand pattern for all nodes, since demands are heavily influenced by social characteristics and depend on the type of business operating within a certain region.

Let flow $d_i(k)$ be the demand at node i at discrete time k . The demand pattern $p_i(k)$ at a node i is defined as $p_i(k) = d_i(k)/v_i$, where v_i is the base demand; i.e. the average or nominal demand for water by the consumers at a node i , measured in flow units. Demand pattern $p_i(k)$ can be used to determine the actual demand $d_i(k)$ at a given time period by multiplying the pattern with the base demand (Rossman, 2000).

Since actual demands are not known, they can be estimated using known flow or pressure measurements. For example, assume that flows situated at the reservoirs and tanks are measured along with the flows of water exiting certain nodes. Without any further information regarding the nature of consumers in the network, the unknown demand pattern $p_i(k)$ of the remaining nodes can be computed using

$$p_i(k) = \frac{\sum_{l \in L} Q_l(k)}{\sum_{i \in F} v_i}, \quad (1)$$

where Q is the flow and L is the set of nodes where demands are measured, v_i is the base demand at node i and F is the set of nodes with unknown demands.

4 ADAPTIVE FORECASTING OF PERIODIC TIME SERIES

As already mentioned, MPC uses a process model in order to compute future states of the system under certain control inputs. For this, a forecast of the hydraulic dynamics is necessary for a specific time-horizon ahead of each time step. By computing an accurate forecast of dynamics in the DWDN, we can further compute a more reliable model based on which the control input is found. Due to the unknown daily water demands, hydraulic dynamics vary in time and can be described as periodic. Various methods exist in the literature in forecasting time-series, such as time series models (e.g. ARMA), regression models, Kalman filtering, neural networks and others (Box et al., 1994,

Kyriakides & Polycarpou, 2007). In this work we examine the use of Fourier series and radial basis functions as the approximation structures in an adaptive framework.

4.1 Fourier series

The Fourier series is the sum of an infinite number of sinusoidal component functions, together with a constant term, and it can represent any periodic function $\chi(k)$ (Ifeachor & Jervis, 1993). By considering only the first K terms and grouping the higher terms in the form of a residual error ϵ , the Fourier series is described as

$$\chi(k) = \theta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^K \theta_i \sin(i\omega k) + \sum_{i=1}^K \theta_{i+K} \cos(i\omega k) + \epsilon, \quad (2)$$

where θ_i , $i = 0, \dots, 2K$, are weight coefficients and $\omega = 2\pi/T_p$ is the fundamental frequency for period T_p . Equation (2) can be written as

$$\chi(k) = \theta^T \xi(k) + \epsilon, \quad (3)$$

for which $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{2K+1}$; $\xi(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{2K+1}$ is the regressor vector given by $\xi(k) = [1, \sin(\omega k), \dots, \sin(K\omega k), \cos(\omega k), \dots, \cos(K\omega k)]^T$.

4.2 Radial basis functions

Radial Basis Functions (RBF) is a type of neural network model that represents a function as a weighted sum of K basis functions, ϕ . One such radial function is the Gaussian

$$\phi(\|k - c_i\|) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\|k - c_i\|^2}{\sigma^2}\right), \quad (4)$$

for which $c \in \mathbb{R}^K$ is a vector of K centre locations, $\|k - c_i\|$ is the distance from the evaluation point to the centre c_i and σ is a parameter constant (Farrell & Polycarpou, 2006). RBF can be therefore represented in a standard form

$$\chi(k) = \sum_{i=1}^K \theta_i \phi(\|k - c_i\|) + \epsilon = \theta^T \xi(k) + \epsilon, \quad (5)$$

where $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^K$ are the weight coefficients for each function, $\xi(k) = [\phi(\|k - c_1\|), \dots, \phi(\|k - c_K\|)]$, and ϵ is again the residual approximation error.

4.3 Adaptive approximation

The objective for the approximation task for both Fourier series and RBF, is to compute the unknown weight coefficients θ . This can be performed on-line, by adapting the weights at each time step, using the gradient method. Specifically, let $\hat{\theta}(k)$ be the parameter estimate of θ at time k , and let

$$e(k) = \hat{\theta}^T(k)\xi(k) - \chi(k) \quad (6)$$

be the output estimation error. Using the standard gradient approach, the update law for $\hat{\theta}(k)$ is given by

$$\hat{\theta}(k+1) = \hat{\theta}(k) - \frac{\gamma\xi(k)e(k)}{\kappa + \xi^T(k)\xi(k)} \quad (7)$$

where $\kappa > 0$ is a design parameter and γ is the adaptive gain.

Once we obtain an accurate model of the periodic variations in the hydraulic dynamics at a particular node, we can then forecast future hydraulic values $\hat{\chi}(k+T)$ that will be used in the prediction horizon of the MPC.

5 MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROLLER (MPC)

According to Camacho & Bordons (2004), MPC uses a model of the system in order to forecast the output at future time instants, computes a control sequence minimizing an objective function and applies the first control signal computed at each time step. Some advantages of this type of controller are its ability to easily handle constraints, it is intuitive to understand and it can handle time-delays as well as consider many inputs and outputs in a straightforward manner. In this section a basic multivariable and constrained MPC formulation of the water quality control problem will be presented. The algorithm is based on the Dynamic Matrix Controller (Prett et al., 1982), adjusted for the time-varying system.

5.1 Process Model

A nominal model of the real DWDN is a simplified network implemented in the EPANET software. Such a model is comprised of structural and operational information acquired from the actual model, as well as statistical information such as the base demands at each node. In this research the software EPANET is exploited to produce the process model, since it is capable of simulating a real DWDN using operational and structural information acquired by engineers.

By using the EPANET simulation engine as well as the recorded and predicted hydraulic values computed adaptively, the process model is build. The process model captures the internal dynamics and is used to compute future quality outputs. Furthermore, because of the linear assumption for quality dynamics,

the principle of superposition can be applied. A suitable model for the MPC controller is the dynamic matrix, composed of the output responses when the input is a discrete-time impulse.

Specifically, the algorithm computes the response for each input with each output. Let ρ and μ be the prediction and control time horizon respectively; N the number of output nodes to be controlled and M the number of chlorine input location. The dynamic matrix $H(k)$ is such that

$$H(k) = \begin{bmatrix} H_{11}(k) & \dots & H_{1M}(k) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ H_{N1}(k) & \dots & H_{NM}(k) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

$H_{ij}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{\rho \times \mu}$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $j = 1, \dots, M$, is a matrix where each column corresponds to the response by a discrete impulse at node i in each future time step, measured at node j . Specifically,

$$H_{ij}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} h_{k,k} & \dots & h_{k,k+\mu-1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ h_{k+\rho-1,k} & \dots & h_{k+\rho-1,k+\mu-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where $h_{a,b} \in \mathbb{R}^1$ is the impulse response coefficient for discrete impulse applied at time b , measured at time a .

5.2 Future Quality Outputs

Let $\hat{y}(k)$ be the predicted output for ρ steps into the future based on information at time k , $f(k)$ is the future responses vector which are caused by the past inputs and $U(k)$ the computed input vector, such that

$$\hat{y}(k) = H(k)U(k) + f(k) + \hat{n}(k), \quad (10)$$

for which $U(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{M\mu}$ and $\hat{y}(k) = [\hat{y}_1(k+1), \dots, \hat{y}_1(k+1+\rho), \dots, \hat{y}_N(k+1), \dots, \hat{y}_N(k+1+\rho)]^T$, for $U(k) = [u_1(k), \dots, u_1(k+\mu), \dots, u_M(k), \dots, u_M(k+\mu)]^T$, and $f(k) = [f_1(k+1), \dots, f_1(k+1+\rho), \dots, f_N(k+1), \dots, f_N(k+1+\rho)]^T$. The disturbance error $\hat{n}(k)$ is the difference between the measured and expected output $\hat{n}(k) = y(k) - \hat{y}(k)$.

5.3 Objective Function

The objective is to compute vector of inputs $U(k)$ which minimizes the difference of output \hat{y} with reference w as well as the magnitude of the input signal $U(k)$. A general expression of the quadratic objective function is

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^{\rho} [\hat{y}(k+j) - w]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{\mu} \lambda [u(k+j)]^2, \quad (11)$$

where λ is a penalizing factor for the input variable variations, and ρ and μ are the prediction and control

horizon time steps. Using (10), the objective function given by (11) can be rewritten in a vector form as

$$V = (\hat{y} - w)^T(\hat{y} - w) + \lambda U^T U \quad (12)$$

$$= (HU + \bar{f} - w)^T(HU + \bar{f} - w) + \lambda U^T U, \quad (13)$$

for $\bar{f} = f + \hat{n}$. By rearranging the terms, this can be rewritten as

$$V = \frac{1}{2}U^T G U + b^T U + f_0, \quad (14)$$

where $G = 2(H^T H + \lambda I)$, $b^T = 2(\bar{f} - w)^T H$ and $f_0 = (\bar{f} - w)^T(\bar{f} - w)$. Physical laws, governmental regulations and safety reasons require a DWDN to operate under certain constraints. The optimization problem is therefore formulated as

$$\min_U \frac{1}{2}U^T G U + b^T U, \quad (15)$$

subject to

$$\underline{U} \leq u(k) \leq \bar{U}, \quad (16)$$

$$\underline{y} - \bar{f} \leq H(k)U(k) \leq \bar{y} - \bar{f}, \quad (17)$$

$$\underline{q} + LU(k-1) \leq TU(k) \leq \bar{q} + LU(k-1), \quad (18)$$

for which \underline{U}, \bar{U} are the lower and upper bounds of the control inputs respectively, \underline{y}, \bar{y} are the lower and upper bounds of the output signal, \underline{q}, \bar{q} are the slew rate lower and upper bounds. T is a matrix in which the diagonal elements are $T_{ii} = 1$ and the elements $T_{i(i-1)} = -1$ except for the cases where $i = \eta(\mu + 2) + 1$ when $\eta = 0, 1, \dots, M$ and μ is the control horizon. $U(k-1)$ is the previous time step control input vector, and L is a matrix whose elements are $T_{ii} = 1$, for $i = \eta(\mu + 2) + 1$ when $\eta = 0, 1, \dots, M$.

Since actuators injecting chlorine can not remove excess chlorine from water, we assume that $\underline{U} = 0$. The lower limit \underline{y} can be considered as a hard limit (e.g. 0.2mg/L), since there must always be a traceable concentration of disinfectant in the network. The upper limit \bar{y} can be virtually any value below the highest concentration allowable set by regulations (e.g. 4.0mg/L). The slew rate limits can be set according to actuator specifications.

This problem can be solved using standard algorithms, such as quadratic programming. Constraints can be easily considered for this optimization problem. Finally, it is known to be a convex problem when the quadratic function has a positive semi-definite Hessian.

Figure 2: A drinking water distribution network with demand flows measured at the nodes {Lake, River, T1, T2, T3, 15, 35, 123, 203} and the chlorine concentration measured at {119, 203}

6 SIMULATION EXAMPLES

To illustrate the adaptive forecasting and the model predictive controller, we conducted a number of simulation studies using a network topology of a DWDN, as provided in the EPANET package, specifically ‘Network 3’ shown in Fig. 2. The network is comprised of two water supplies as well as three tanks and two pumps working on a daily schedule. Chlorine booster stations as well as hydraulic and quality dynamic sensors are installed in the network.

Algorithms were implemented in MATLAB, using the EPANET toolkit. We assume that there is a nominal water DWDN, modelled in EPANET, representing the actual system. The nominal network has similar topology with the real network and is set with the same operational characteristics and with off-line computed base demand averages for each junction. In reality the actual system is subject to disturbances, and the values in the model which were computed off-line may be slightly different from the actual ones.

6.1 Forecasting hydraulic dynamics

The adaptive approximation must learn the hydraulic dynamics, up to a certain level such that the approximation error will be relatively small. Applying control input to the real system requires that the true hydraulic dynamics are not significantly different from the estimated ones. In a different case, the control input would not be able to regulate the concentrations at the points where the quality sensors are installed.

The ability of the adaptive approximation to learn the demand pattern is shown in the following example, by computing the unknown coefficients of Fourier series and RBF. We assume that the flow values at the nodes labelled in Fig. 2 are measured in each time step. By using (1), we compute the unknown demand pattern $p_i(k)$ for the remaining nodes

Figure 3: Adaptively approximated demand patterns using Fourier series and RBF, after a 10-day period with zero and 40% disturbances

in the system. This information is used in the adaptive forecasting, in order to estimate the future demand values.

The adaptive approximation was learning data for a 10-day period, for which each flow sensor reported every 5 minutes. The weights are adjusted in each time step in order to capture the hydraulic dynamics. The Fourier series considered the first $K = 50$ terms, whereas the RBF considered 120 centres between $[0, 24]$ with $\sigma = 0.2$. Specifically in the RBF the value of time step k changes to the corresponding daily time. Different scenarios were examined for which the demand patterns in each unmeasured node were influenced by random disturbances. The base scenario is when the computed demand pattern is same to each demand pattern at each unmeasured node. When for example 40% disturbances are considered, the actual flow at a time step at an unobserved node is within $\mp 40\%$ of the estimated flow. The computed weights are used to find the demand pattern that will be applied to the future time steps of the system. The results are presented in Fig. 3. We observe that both approximation structures manage to learn the hydraulic characteristics, even when the nodes are influenced by some disturbances. However, the RBF is not as robust as the Fourier series in large disturbances.

Another issue worth considering is that adaptive approximation does not stop; therefore it is able to respond to changes in the network or consumption behaviour. Furthermore, by using extra information regarding the nature of consumers, it is possible to compute demand pattern models for groups of nodes that are similar to the actual patterns.

Figure 5: The estimated and measured chlorine concentrations in node 203, under a $\mp 30\%$ demand pattern and $\mp 5\%$ base demand disturbance

6.2 Controller demonstration

In this experiment we demonstrate the ability of the controller to regulate the chlorine concentrations at specific nodes in the network, by adjusting chlorine concentrations at the point of injection. We assume that the adaptive approximation was performed with the Fourier series for a 10-day period. In order to show the control effect, for the first 48 hours the input is a step signal of $0.4mg/L$. Afterwards, the controller is switched on. The prediction and control time horizon is $\rho = \mu = 48$ hours and $\lambda = 10$.

We assume that locations where chlorine injection actuators are placed are at the ‘River’ and the ‘Lake’, whereas chlorine concentration sensors are located at nodes ‘119’ and ‘203’. Figure 4 shows the input and output signals for a period of 90 hours, with zero disturbances in the demand patterns. The disturbance error $\hat{n}(k)$ is not taken by the MPC into consideration. The control task is to regulate the output signals to $0.25mg/L$, while input signals are between $[0, 4]mg/L$ and output signals between $[0.2, 0.5]mg/L$. The periods where no chlorine is injected at the Lake are because the pumps are shut during those hours. We note that the controller may take into consideration more nodes than those whose chlorine concentration is actually measured, in order to achieve better spatial distribution of chlorine across the network.

In some situations it is impossible for the quadratic program to find a solution which does not violate the constraints. When this occurs, the controller can select a predetermined input signal, or use a different optimization method with relaxed constraints. The controller switches back to quadratic optimization program, when a feasible solution can be computed.

When the hydraulic dynamics are influenced by disturbances, the measured chlorine concentrations in the output locations are different that those estimated by the model. For example, Fig. 5 demonstrates the measured and estimated outputs in a node, for a period of time after the controller is enabled. The con-

Figure 4: A step input is applied for 48 hours, and then the constrained MPC is activated with 48-hour control horizon

troller is under the constraints used in the previous example, which are relaxed in case of a not feasible solution. We assumed for the simulation that the demand patterns were influenced by a $\pm 30\%$ disturbance, whereas the base demands by a $\pm 5\%$. We observe that in certain time-steps, the measured chlorine concentration dropped below the $200\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ limit, because disturbances significantly influenced hydraulic dynamics. Future studies will examine the use of a disturbance models to achieve a more robust feedback control of the system.

7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have studied the problem of quality control for drinking water distribution networks, by exploiting the periodic nature of hydraulic dynamics. The approach presented is based on an online MPC framework. Because the actual system is significantly time-varying as it is driven by unknown demands, future states of the distribution system are unknown; therefore the future hydraulic dynamics, and by projection the water demands, need to be predicted.

The hydraulic dynamics, which are typically of periodic nature, are represented by a Fourier series and RBF with online parameter estimation of the unknown coefficients. Both approximation structures are suitable for computing daily demand patterns, as shown in the experiments, even under the influence of disturbances. The predicted demand patterns can be directly applied to simulation models that numerically solve the hydraulic and quality equations for the future time steps.

When the adaptive approximation has learned the hydraulics, the controller is activated to regulate the chlorine concentrations across the DWDN. The ob-

jective function is in a quadratic form, and the optimization program minimizes the difference between the future output concentration and a regulation concentration, as well as minimizes the input concentrations.

Certain constraints may be applied to guarantee that the input and output are within those bounds. The optimization algorithms may consider regulating all nodes in the network, even though only some are actually monitored. Better hydraulic forecasting methods as well as better water demand estimators would provide more accurate models of the DWDN to be used with the MPC, which will assist in achieving better control of the system.

8 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by the Research Promotion Foundation (Cyprus) and by the University of Cyprus Research Fund.

REFERENCES

- Agha, S. R. 2006. Use of goal programming and integer programming for water quality management—A case study of Gaza Strip. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 174(3), 1991–1998.
- Boccelli, D. L., Tryby, M. E., Uber, J. G., Rossman, L. A., Zierolf, M. L., & Polycarpou, M. M. 1998. Optimal scheduling of booster disinfection in water distribution systems. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 124(2), 99–111.
- Box, G. E., Jenkins, G. M., & Reinsel, G. C. 1994. *Time series analysis: Forecasting and control*. Prentice Hall, 3rd edition.

- Brdys, M. A., Chang, T., & Duzinkiewicz, K. 2001. Intelligent model predictive control of chlorine residuals in water distribution systems. In D. Phelps & G. Sehlke (Eds.), *ASCE World Water Congress 2001*, volume 111 (pp. 391–401): ASCE.
- Brdys, M. A., Chang, T., Duzinkiewicz, K., & Chotkowski, W. 2000. Hierarchical control of integrated quality and quantity in water distribution systems. In R. H. Hotchkiss & M. Glade (Eds.), *ASCE Water Resources 2000*, volume 104 (pp. 193–202): ASCE.
- Camacho, F. & Bordons, C. 2004. *Model Predictive Control*. Springer, 2nd edition.
- Chang, T., Brdys, M. A., & Duzinkiewicz, K. 2003. Decentralized robust model predictive control of chlorine residuals in drinking water distribution systems. In P. Bizier & P. DeBarry (Eds.), *ASCE World Water Congress 2003*, volume 118 (pp. 255–264): ASCE.
- Constans, S., Bremond, B., & Morel, P. 2003. Simulation and control of chlorine levels in water distribution networks. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 129(2), 135–145.
- Cozzolino, L., Pianese, D., & Pirozzi, F. 2005. Control of DBPs in water distribution systems through optimal chlorine dosage and disinfection station allocation. *Desalination*, 176(1), 113–125.
- Dandy, G. & Hewitson, C. 2000. Optimizing hydraulics and water quality in water distribution networks using genetic algorithms. In R. H. Hotchkiss & M. Glade (Eds.), *ASCE Water Resources 2000*, volume 104 (pp. 211–220): ASCE.
- EC 1998. 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption. *Official Journal of the European Communities*, 330(5), 12.
- EPA 1998. National primary drinking water regulations: Disinfectants and disinfection byproducts; final rule. *Federal Register*, 63(241), 69390–69476.
- Farrell, J. A. & Polycarpou, M. M. 2006. *Adaptive Approximation Based Control: Unifying Neural, Fuzzy and Traditional Adaptive Approximation Approaches*. Wiley.
- Ifeachor, E. & Jervis, B. 1993. *Digital Signal Processing: a Practical Approach*. Addison-Wesley.
- Kyriakides, E. & Polycarpou, M. 2007. *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, volume 35, chapter Short Term Electric Load Forecasting: A Tutorial, (pp. 391–418). Springer Berlin / Heidelberg.
- Morris, R. D., Audet, A. M., Angelillo, I. F., Chalmers, T. C., & Mosteller, F. 1992. Chlorination, chlorination by-products, and cancer: a meta-analysis. *American Journal of Public Health*, 82(7), 955–963.
- Munavalli, G. R. & Kumar, M. S. M. 2003. Optimal scheduling of multiple chlorine sources in water distribution systems. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 129(6), 493–504.
- Ostfeld, A. & Salomons, E. 2006. Conjunctive optimal scheduling of pumping and booster chlorine injections in water distribution systems. *Engineering Optimization*, 38(3), 337–352.
- Prasad, T. D., Walters, G. A., & Savic, D. A. 2004. Booster disinfection of water supply networks: Multiobjective approach. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 130(5), 367–376.
- Prett, D., Ramaker, B., & Cutler, C. 1982. Dynamic matrix control method. US Patent 4,349,869.
- Propato, M. & Uber, J. G. 2004. Linear least-squares formulation for operation of booster disinfection systems. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 130(1), 53–62.
- Rossmann, L. 2000. *EPANET 2 Users Manual*. National Risk Management Research Laboratory, Office of Research and Development, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, OH 45268.
- Sakarya, A. B. A. & Mays, L. W. 2000. Optimal operation of water distribution pumps considering water quality. *ASCE Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 126(4), 210–220.
- Walski, T., Chase, D., & Savic, D. 2001. *Water Distribution Modeling*. Haestad Press, 1st edition.
- Wang, Z., Polycarpou, M., Uber, J., & Shang, F. 2001. Adaptive periodic control for chlorine residual maintenance in drinking water distribution networks. In *Proceedings of the 40th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control, 2001*, volume 5 (pp. 4069–4074 vol.5).
- Wang, Z., Polycarpou, M., Uber, J., & Shang, F. 2006. Adaptive control of water quality in water distribution networks. *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, 14(1), 149–156.